

Strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in Ebonyi state colleges of education

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Abstract

The study determined strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using Young Farmers Club roles in Ebonyi State Colleges of Education. Survey research design was used for the study. The whole population of 23 respondents was used comprising of five lecturers and 18 agricultural education students, who are members of Young Farmers Club in the colleges of education. It was a census as there was no sampling. The instrument for data collection was; Strategies for Improving the Teaching and Learning Agricultural Education using Young Farmers Club Role in the College of Education in Ebonyi State (SITLARUYFCR). It was validated by three (3) experts; Two in Agricultural Education unit of Technology and Vocational Education Department; and one in Science Education Department in Measurement and Evaluation Unit of Ebonyi State University. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyzed the research questions. It was found out that all the eight items in field trip were accepted by the respondents as strategies for teaching and learning agricultural education while eight (8) items in meeting/discussion, and eight (8) items for inculcating positive attitude were all accepted as best method for delivery of both practical and knowledge wise in agricultural education. it was recommended that such youth programme should be adopted for teaching and learning agricultural education in their curriculum among others.

Keywords: Strategies; Improving; Young farmer; Club roles; Agricultural Education; Teaching and learning

1. Introduction

Young Farmer's club roles is the plans to bridge in the body of knowledge, skills, experiences, as such that effective production will be the outcome. Amed (2021) see strategies as general knowledge, attitude, skills and understanding that are geared toward occupation in various sections in economic development. Strategies in the contest of this study is the way to close the gap in teaching and learning process in agricultural education that can help to improve its delivery system for achieving practical skills, knowledge wise, attitudinal understanding that can lead to massive food production for the masses. In another development, improving is to change for better, make things more attractive, practicable, despite all the hindrance facing it. Ogba (2022), maintains that improving is worthwhile venture, positive approach that brings in need for teaching and learning in such body of the knowledge and skill. He stressed that Agricultural Education knowledge and practice cannot remain static but change for better, and attract others for production purposes. Ogba and Ndem (2020) see improvement as an assessment practice, as standardized test and observation both in practice and skill of practical teaching and learning. Improving in the contest of this paper is the standard where agricultural education is delivered to students with more practical steps for better result. Ogba (2023) see teaching and learning as a dynamic process for reformation, and synergies between training and skill development producers. He stress that teaching and learning is a guide between more knowledgeable people to less knowledgeable

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one that can lead to change in behavior. Teaching and learning in the context of this study is the process of imparting knowledge in Agricultural education to students that are offering it as their course of study.

In another, development, Agricultural education is an integral part of vocational education. Olaton (2021) see vocational education as a course for those that need it and want to use it and develop the skills they want to use in life. Ogba, (2023) stress that agricultural education teaching and learning requires field practical, and classroom approach in the colleges of education for effective delivery, he maintains that field laboratory is where skills and knowledge based are developed for production and management. Ogba & Eze (2020) view the teaching and learning of Agricultural education as problem solving method which cannot end without innovation as change agent. Mohamed (2018) stress that Agricultural education teaching and learning requires youth program, which gears towards skill, development, knowledge and understanding among themselves for agricultural production. Food and Agricultural Organization (F.A.O) (2022) stress that young farmer club is youth organization that have similar characteristics with agricultural education program. F.A.O (2022) stress that young farmers club has influence in the social economic development of any nation. Mohamed, (2014) is of the view that agricultural education is a formal education program, that is taught and learnt in colleges of education, with similar production operation, innovation with young farmers' club roles. In another development, Abubakar (2018) is of the opinion that national curriculum for colleges of education has Agricultural Education as a course of study. Tybo (2018) see the philosophy of national commission for colleges of education in agricultural education that produce Nigerian certificate in education graduate, as similar to that of young farmer club in agricultural operation and self-reliance. Therefore, it calls for research investigation, to establish empirically, the roles of Young Farmers Clubs as a strategy for improving teaching and learning Agric education.

This youth organization exist in Ebonyi state colleges of education, Okorie (2014) maintains that the young farmers club is an interest motivator and creator for changing negative attitude of youth towards agricultural education teaching as well as production of food as a serious business. However, Osualar (2000) see role as the function and the duty of something, in a bid to develop its potential. Role in the context of this study is the activities of young farmers club, supposed to render to their members in terms of guiding them, in discussing /meeting in the field of agricultural production, Odo (2021) see field trip of young farmers club as the way of changing student (youth) negative attitude to farming and accept agricultural education practice in the production of food, processing them, distributing them, marketing among others. Ogba and Umaru (2000) see agricultural education objective in tertiary institution as achievable only when the students are exposed more in practical field work and as well sponsored by many private agro industries. Therefore, the need arise to establish the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using Young Farmers' club roles in colleges of education in field trips, meeting/discussion and inculcating positive attitude in agricultural by the students.

1.1. Young Farmers Club Roles

Figure 1 Role(s) Index of YFC to members

1.2. Purpose of Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the role of the young farmers club as strategies for improving the teaching and learning of the agricultural education in college of education in Ebonyi state. Specifically, the study tends to:

- Determine the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in field trips to her members in colleges of education.
- Investigate the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in discussion and meetings with her members in colleges of education.
- Determine the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in inculcating positive attitude toward agricultural education student in colleges of education.

1.3. Research Question

- What are the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in field trips to her members in college of education?
- What are the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in discussion and meetings with her members in college of education?
- What are the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in inculcating positive attitude toward agricultural education student in college of education?

2. Methodology

The study was carried out in Ebonyi State, which is bounded in the East with Cross River, South with Abia State; West with Enugu State, and North with Benue State. It is one of the states in the Southeast region Nigeria. The study was within Ebonyi state college of education Ikwo, which exist in the central education zone in the state.

2.1. Population and Sample

The population for the study consist of five lecturers in Agricultural Education Department and 18 students, who are members of young farmers' club in the college of education. The entire population was used as the sample, since the population is small and manageable.

2.2. Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was structured questionnaire, which contains 24 item statements, structured on 4point rating scale of (a) Strongly needed - 4 (b) Moderately needed - 3 (c) Slightly needed - 2 (d) Not needed - 1.

2.3. Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was given to three experts for face validation. Two from Agricultural Education experts in the Department of Technology and Vocational Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation, Unit in the Department of Science Education all in Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki. The validators were directed to check the suitability, relevance and clarity of the items. The corrections, observations and suggestions of the validators were taken in final draft of the instrument.

2.4. Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was determined by carrying out similar study at Enugu State using three (3) lecturers in Agricultural Education and five students in Agricultural Education in college of education in Enugu state, the data collected were analyzed using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient which was used to determine the internal consistency of the items which yielded 0.79.

2.5. Method of Data Collected

The researchers personally collected the data which they administered to the respondents; lecturers and students. While 23 copies of the questionnaire distributed was returned and properly filled, and was used for data analysis, this represented 100% return rate.

2.6. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. A mean score of 2.50 was used as cut off point or criterion level for decision taken. Thus, any item with mean score of 2.50 and above is regarded as strongly needed by the respondents, while below 2.50 was regarded as not needed.

3. Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

3.1. Research Question 1: What are the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in field trips to her members in college of education?

Table 1 Analysis of Mean Ratin of the Responses of Members of YFC on Field Trip

S/N	Questionnaire Items (Field Trips)	(\bar{x})	SD	Decision
1	Visitation to poultry farm with 3 sections (Broiler, Layers & Hatchers)	3.25	1.35	Strongly needed
2	Visitation to fish farm with 3 sections (fingerling, givinal and Matured section)	3.18	1.41	Strongly needed
3	Visitation to piggery farm with 3 sections (Piglet section, pregnant pig section and meting section)	3.13	1.33	Strongly needed

4	Visitation to plantain farm with 3 sections (Cocoa, Cola nut and para rubber)	3.98	1.53	Strongly needed
5	Visitation to research institute for tuber, roots, fruits (seed) (Umudike and Ibadan Colleges of Education)	3.95	1.33	Strongly needed
6	Visitation to oil palm seed multiplication and breeding programme.	3.42	1.63	Strongly needed
7	Visitation to agricultural research institute (Ibadan)	3.21	1.43	Strongly needed
8	Visitation to integrated complex farm (Ota)	3.41	1.55	Strongly needed

Table 1, The strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in field trips to her members in college of education in Ebonyi State has eight (8) items and all the items were accepted by the respondents as needed. The highest mean scores and standard deviation ranging from 3.13 to 3.98 and standard deviation range of 1.33, to 1.53 as the highest mean scores and standard deviation items in field trip. This signifies that the respondents strongly needed the field trips to her members as strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education in the colleges of education in Ebonyi State.

3.2. Research Question 2: What are the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in discussion and meetings with her members in college of education?

Table 2 Analysis of Mean Rating of the Responses of Members of YFC on Meeting and Discussion

S/N	Questionnaire Items (Meeting/Discussion with Experts)	(\bar{x})	SD	Decision
1	Arrange meeting and discussion for her members with crop science experts	3.32	1.42	Strongly needed
2	Arrange for meeting with poultry experts production with her members	3.12	1.25	Strongly needed
3	Fixing discussion in workshops for her members	3.26	1.34	Strongly needed
4	Fixing discussion with priggery experts for her members	3.14	1.32	Strongly needed
5	Fixing discussion with vetenary experts for her members	2.52	1.41	moderately needed
6	Arrange for meeting with crop experts for her members	2.51	1.17	moderately needed
7	Arrange for discussion with vegetable and fruit production experts for her members	3.13	1.26	Strongly needed
8	Arrange for discussion with extension agents with her members	2.94	1.33	Strongly needed

The table II showed that item 1 has the highest mean rating of 3.32 and standard deviation of 1.42. while item 5 and 6 has mean score rating of 2.52 and 2.51 and standard deviation of 1.41 and 1.17, which indicated moderately needed in discussion and meeting for her members. This implies that discussion / meetings were needed by respondents since, all were in agreement that this discussion and meeting regarding agricultural education improves its teaching and learning.

3.3. Research Question 3: What are the strategies for improving the teaching and learning of agricultural education using young farmers club roles in inculcating of positive attitude toward agricultural education students in colleges of education?

Table 3 Analysis of Mean Ratin of the Responses of Members of YFC on Inculcating Positive Attitude

S/N	Questionnaire Items (Inculcating Positive Attitude)	(\bar{x})	SD	Decision
1	Young farmers club provide means of earning money for her members.	2.64	1.41	Strongly needed
2	Young farmers club provide skills of agricultural production for practice with her members	3.32	1.53	Strongly needed
3	Young farmers club motivate members to participate in farming activities	3.51	1.67	Strongly needed
4	Young farmers club is a well-organized group for agricultural development	3.40	1.81	Strongly needed
5	Field trip organized by young farmers club encourages the public to join and start farming practice.	3.41	1.72	Strongly needed
6	I like young farmers club because it provide job opportunity for her members	3.33	1.62	Strongly needed
7	Discussion/meeting between expert farmers and her members makes it an interesting organization	3.32	1.81	Strongly needed
8	Young farmers club practicalize all aspect of agricultural education with her members	3.65	1.82	Strongly needed

Table 3 shows that item 8 has the highest mean score rating of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.82, as highly needed positive attitude towards her members. While item 1 has mean score rating of 2.64 as the lowest and standard deviation of 1.41 as moderately needed, this implies that attitude and interest of the respondents improves teaching and learning of agricultural education.

4. Discussion of Findings

Table 1 and research question 1: It was discovered from the findings shown in research question 1 that most areas of visitations identified were agreed upon by the agricultural education students as essential strategies for improving teaching and learning of agricultural education in colleges of education and creating awareness in different areas of agricultural education. The findings of this study was in agreement with that of Amed (2018), who noted that young farmers club organization inculcate agricultural education skills through field trips for her members to restore their confidence in agricultural programmes, productions among others. The above views of Ahmed corroborates with the idea of Ogba (2020) who maintains that giving agricultural education students opportunities to interact with experts in different area of agricultural sector of interest will encourage them to learn more in the area of their vocation. The findings show that students have choice to make as to what they need most and areas. This is in line with view of Oliation (2021) who observed that when it comes to skills development to students, (Job skills) many students will like to enroll in such practical programme to equip them. This study is in line with the study of Ogba and Eze (2021) who see agricultural education teaching and learning as problem solving when it is necessary to them and will benefit them in reviewing the style of teaching and learning agricultural education by students in young farmers club with her members are mainly engaging them in field of agricultural practice like discussion and meeting experts in different areas in the field, visiting different agricultural sector, agri-technologies, animal production center, research institutes and inculcating positive attitude to students by attracting them and retaining them in the areas. This study is in line with the study of Ogba (2023), who noted that agricultural education utilizing the roles of young farmers club is injecting job training to students in different areas of agricultural production in the colleges of education. It is important to note that good teaching and learning style ensures that skills are properly arranged system to the students who need them.

4.1. Table II Research question 2:

The use of discussion and meeting with her members and experts. The result presented in research question (2) revealed that Young Farmers Club roles were needed strongly by Agricultural Education students in eight (8) items

ranging from crop science experts, animal science experts, farmer education and extension experts, among others. This study is in line with the study of Osualar (2000), who stressed that Young Farmers club guide their members in meetings and discussion in different field of Agriculture. The study is also in line with the study of Okorie (2014) who stress that Young Farmers Club is an interest motivator for students towards Agricultural operations after meeting and discussion with the students in the field, which guide members. This study is in line with that of Abubakar (2018), who maintained that the curriculum of Agricultural Education as course in colleges of education is similar to that of Young Farmers Club objectives which will gear towards motivating and students in Agricultural operations when guided by experts in various areas of agricultural production.

4.2. Table 3, Research Question 3:

The result presented in research question 3, on the roles of Young Farmers club in inculcating positive attitude towards agricultural education students within her members. revealed that Young farmers Club roles were needed strongly by Agricultural Education students in eight (8) items, which implies that attitude of respondents to improves the teaching and learning of Agricultural Education when the members are activated in skills, knowledge and positive thinking towards been self-reliance and productive in their areas of specialization. This study is in line with the study of Odo (2021), who see Young Farmers Club roles with members and experts in Agriculture as direct link in making money for her members, since they will acquire practical skills that can earn a living with them and change their negative attitude to positive ones in Agricultural production. This study is also in line with the study of Ogba and Egbe (2023), who see the teaching and learning of Agricultural Education with the use of Young Farmers Club roles as a life changer services in positive attitude, problem for participating in farming operation is solved, which will provide job opportunities for members. Experts guide members in securing jobs in Agro-allied companies and technologies.

This study is in line with the study of Ogba (2022), who see agricultural education as a course that has field laboratory where the classroom laboratories are subjected to practical skills and knowledge demonstration, in crops production and animals. He sees teaching and learning of the course with the roles of Young Farmers Club as ways of involving different experts to contributes to the development of her members and reduce unemployment of their members. The eight items in the roles if Young Farmers club in inculcating positive attitude towards agricultural education students received needed strongly by the respondents

5. Conclusion

It is important to provide the needed vocational skills to agricultural education students that will enable them to become self-reliant so that when they graduate from college of education, they can lay hands in any of the skills in agricultural education that they were exposed to in the field. The national commission for colleges of education should provide reformed curriculum in agricultural education that can enhance its teaching and learning with skills training in youth programmes, so that after graduation, they can lay hand on agricultural production as great farmers in the nation for food security and development.

Recommendations

Researchers recommended that young farmers club (roles)as youth programme should be inculcated into the curriculum of agricultural education in colleges of education for both practical skills, integrated knowledge wise, and production.

It was also, recommended that youth club like, young farmers club roles should have an attachment in their programme to enable them tend help to students in tertiary institution in technology, industrial based, Agro-technology among others.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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